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Effects of Irrigation on Cotton Genotypes in the Arid Environment of Dera Ismail Khan

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Abstract

Drought stress is a major ecological factor that negatively impacts cotton yield and quality. In this scenario, drought-tolerant cotton cultivars with zero tillage could be the best option. A field experiment was conducted in 2017 at Cotton Research Station, Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan to evaluate the effects of four irrigation intervals on yield and fiber characteristics of three cotton genotypes. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with split plot arrangements replicated thrice. Four irrigation intervals (i.e. 10 days interval, 15 days interval, 20 days interval and 25 days interval) were allotted to main plots while cotton genotypes (MNH-886, CRIS-342, and CRIS-134) were assigned to subplots having 10 m×3 m. Results showed that cotton yield and fiber characteristics had significant response to irrigation intervals and genotypes. Main effects revealed that 10 days irrigation interval produced higher sympodial branches and plant height as compared to other irrigation intervals. Higher bolls per plant, boll weight, seed cotton, ginning outturn (GOT %), lint index, fiber length, fiber strength, and micronaire were achieved from irrigation interval of 25 days. Interaction effects revealed that variety CRIS-134 with 25 days irrigation interval produced greater bolls per plant, boll weight, seed cotton, ginning outturn (GOT %), lint index, fiber length, fiber strength, and micronaire compared to all other combinations. Thus it was concluded that the genotype CRIS-134 with 25 days irrigation interval is more advantageous, adaptable and had the potential to optimize cotton yield and quality in agro-ecological conditions of Dera Ismail Khan

Keywords: ZT cotton, irrigation intervals, varieties, yield, fiber characteristics

Introduction

Cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) is an important cash crop of Pakistan (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2007; Ashraf *et al.*, 2018). It supplies raw materials to textile industries and is called silver-fiber due to its unique quality (Arshad and Anwar, 2007). Cotton is used in garments, medicines, and furnishings of homes. Pakistan is the 5th biggest cotton producers after India, China, United States, and Brazil (Statista, 2018). However, Pakistan is not producing sufficient raw materials for national textile mills. Accordingly, Pakistan is the first among leading cotton importing countries of the world such as Bangladesh, Turkey, Vietnam, China, and Indonesia (APTMA, 2018). In Pakistan, the cotton cultivated area has reached 3 million hectares; share in GDP to 1.5% and value added to agriculture 7.0% (MNFSR, 2015). The present area under cotton cultivation with low production per unit area cannot meet even the domestic requirement of the growing population. Since extension of the existing area under cotton may not be possible as already occupied by major crops such as wheat, rice, maize, and sugarcane, the possible alternative is to increase cotton yield on the existing area. There are several factors that

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affect cotton productivity; however, genotype and water are the two key factors that can affect cotton more seriously than all other factors.

Cotton yield can be optimized with suitable genotype and optimum use of irrigation water; however, there is an acute shortage of irrigation water and of high yielding genetically pure genotype. The current water crisis in agriculture gives emphasis on efficient use of water resources (Azevedo *et al.*, 2012). Since, water consumption is more in conventional tillage than in conservation tillage (Hearn, 2000); drought tolerant genotype grown with conservation practices may give economic yield with limited irrigation water at reduced cost of cultivation (Xi-ping *et al.*, 2004; Hackwell *et al.*, 1991; CTIC, 2004; Shipitalo and Owens 2006; Usman *et al.*, 2013). Increasing water use efficiency by potential genotype grown with conservation tillage can be an important criterion for enhancing yield under stressful water environment. Several researchers have confirmed positive impact of the zero-tillage system on cotton quality, economics and water use efficiency (Hulugalle *et al.*, 2004; Tursonov, 2009). More recent studies revealed that increased cotton yield and quality under zero tillage system might be due to improved water use efficiency (WUE), soil fertility, and nutrient status (Hulugalle *et al.*, 2004).

Cotton is a warm-season crop that needs a regular supply of water, either from irrigation or rainfall. Successful cotton production depends on availability of water. The world scientists are in search of low inputs agriculture including wise use of irrigation water to optimize production from existing limited water (Xi-Ping *et al.*, 2004). Using inadequate water for enhancing cotton productivity is one of the major challenges for agriculturists (Tennakoon and Milroy, 2003; Tang *et al.* (2005). WUE can be improved by adopting best irrigation management practices (Goyne and McIntyre, 2001). Effective agronomic practice needs to be explored which has the potential to enhance WUE and cotton yield (Mcalavy, 2004). Since the study area, Dera Ismail Khan, is an arid region and has limited rainfall in addition to low organic matter status of the soil, high yielding genotype grown with zero tillage could be a viable option for efficient use of inadequate irrigation water. Moreover, a drought-tolerant cotton cultivar should be searched being well fit in the region, particularly genetically modified high yielding and drought tolerant variety (Bt). CRIS-342 is an early maturing drought-tolerant genotype which takes about 40-45 days to appearance of first flower followed by CRIS-134 (Baloch *et al.*, 2014). It is also high yielding Bt variety and performs well even in adverse environmental conditions. MNH-886 (Bt.) is an upland cotton cultivar (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) developed through hybridization of three parents [(FH - 207 × MNH-770) × Bollgard-1] at Central Cotton Research Station Multan, Pakistan. It is high yielding and disease resistant (CLCuVD) variety. CRIS-134 is an early maturing Bt variety having higher bolls per plant, seed cotton yield, and more lint index. Since a little research was done before to investigate the effect of irrigation intervals on different transgenic cultivars under zero tillage; therefore, the present research was aimed to examine the response of cotton cultivars under limited water condition, and to look for best performing Bt. variety of cotton under no-tillage system.

Materials and Methods

Experimental site

The study was conducted in 2017 at Cotton Research Station, Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan (31° 49' N, 70° 55' E, 165 m above sea level). The soil of the study area is Hyperthermic, and Typic Torrfluvents, moderately saline, less fertile, and needs irrigation for crop production (Soil Survey Staff 2009). The area is situated in the arid region where canal water is used for irrigation.

It is hot and dry in summer with moderate rain during monsoon season; March, July, and August are the wettest months. The experimental soil was strongly calcareous in nature. The detail physico-chemical properties are given in Table 2. Weather data was monitored on Meteorological Station located near the study site. Detail about seasonal temperature and rainfall are presented in Table 1.

Experimental procedure

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with split-plot arrangement replicated thrice. Irrigation was given according to treatment detail with 10, 15, 20, and 25 days interval each at a depth of 7.5cm.

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In this way, the quantity of irrigation used in 10, 15, 20, and 25 days interval during the growing season was 1125, 750, 560, and 450 mm, respectively. Irrigation interval (i.e. 10, 15, 20, & 25 days) were the main plot treatment and varieties (viz. CRIS-134, MNH-886, CRIS-342) the subplots. Each subplot consisted of four rows of 10 m length and 0.75 m intra row width. All the subplots were isolated from each other by making bunds around them so that the amount of irrigation for one subplot did not affect the amount of irrigation for another subplot. All plots were managed uniformly regarding land preparation, sowing method, irrigation, pest control, and fertilization. Lines were drawn with cottonseed planter in the field previously occupied with wheat. Cotton was sown with dibbling method in wheat residues without land preparation. Sowing was done on May 28, 2017, using seed rate of 20 kg ha⁻¹. Four seeds were sown hill⁻¹ with 75cm in rows spaced 22.5cm. Irrigation was given through canals. Thinning was done 20 days after emergence by leaving one seedling hill⁻¹. Fertilizer, i.e. N, P and K fertilizers were given at the rate of 150:60:50 kg/ha. Whole P and potash as TSP and SOP sources, respectively, were given during field preparation, whereas N as urea was given in three equal splits, i.e., i.e. at thinning (twenty days after sowing), flowering (62 DAS) and boll formation (90 DAS) stage. All subplots were treated equally regarding sowing method, insect/pests control, and fertilization. Harvesting was done on 30th November 2017.

Procedure for data recording

The parameters studied were plant height (cm), sympodia per plant, bolls per plant, boll weight (g), seed cotton yield (kg ha⁻¹), GOT (%), fiber length (mm), fiber strength (g tex⁻¹) and fiber micronaire (g inch⁻¹). Six randomly selected plants were tagged in each subplot at maturity for measuring plant height and recorded average plant height (cm), Sympodial branches, bolls per plant. Total bolls on each plant were counted manually and then averaged. Fifty bolls were randomly collected from each plot and were weighed to record average boll weight. Seed cotton yields per plot were weighed with an electronic balance and converted into kg ha⁻¹. Ginning out turn was recorded by taking seed cotton samples from each plot. After cleaning and sun drying the samples were then ginned with electric ginning machine. The lint attained was weighed, and ginning outturn (GOT) and lint index were calculated by the following formulas.

$$\text{GOT (\%)} = \frac{\text{Lint yield (kg)}}{\text{Seed cotton yield (kg)}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Lint index} = \frac{\text{Lint \%} \times \text{seed index}}{100 - \text{lint \%}}$$

Fiber quality such as fiber length, fiber strength (g tex⁻¹), and fiber micronaire (μg inch⁻¹) was found out through high-volume instrument system taking 50 g sample of lint from each treatment.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses of the data were performed as per ANOVA techniques (Steel *et al.*, 1997), and significant results were subjected to LSD test for mean comparison using MSTATC software (MSTATC, 1991).

Results and Discussion

Plant height (cm)

Plant height showed a significant response to irrigation intervals. However, it did not respond to varieties and irrigation × varieties interaction (Table 3). Results revealed irrigation applied with 10 days intervals showed the maximum plant height followed by 15, 20, and 25 days irrigation intervals. Regression analysis revealed quadratic response to irrigation intervals (Fig. 1a). Plant height decreased as the irrigation interval increased from 10 to 25. Higher plant height with frequent irrigations might be due to the growing of more nodes and reduced canopy temperature. Cotton is a tap root crop; received frequent irrigations resulted in taller plants. Moisture regimes had divergent influence on the growth of cotton plants. Water stress produced shorter plants because the plants under appropriate irrigations showed excessive main-stem nodes ensuing in taller plants. In moisture stress conditions vegetative growth was reduced due to lower leaf area index (Pettigrew, 2004; Kar et

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al., 2005). Wiggins (2012) and Siskani *et al.* (2015) communicated similar findings which reported that water stress reduced plant height of cotton. They further reported that irrigation applied as per requirement of the crop resulted in higher plant height.

Sympodial branches per plant

Fruit-bearing or reproductive branches in cotton, are called sympodial branches. Irrigation intervals and cultivars effects were significant while interaction was not significant regarding sympodial branches per plant (Table 3). Crop irrigated with 10 days interval produced more sympodia as compared to the rest of the given treatments, i.e. 15, 20 and 25 days intervals. Cultivar CRIS-134 had a higher number of sympodia as compared to CRIS-342 and MNH-886 both having a similar number of sympodial branches. Regression analysis showed that sympodia plant⁻¹ had a quadratic response to irrigation intervals (Fig. 1b). The trend line showed a similar pattern as mentioned for plant height. Sympodia per plant decreased with the increase in irrigation interval from 10 to 25 days. Higher sympodia per plant might be due to better water availability of nutrients and maximum water utilization at fruit-bearing stage. The genotype CRIS-134 is of bushy type, maintained 2-3 monopodia and number of sympodial branches per plant under fewer frequencies of irrigation. These results were in line with findings obtained by Maqsood *et al.* (2006) who concluded that sufficient interval of irrigation to cotton produced more sympodial branches. Copur (2006) reported that sympodial branches per plant were different for different varieties. Pedroza and Flores (1998) arrived at analogous results and concluded that irrigation intervals affected sympodial branches substantially, whereas cotton varieties of different genetic makeup produced great variation in the number of sympodia.

Bolls plant⁻¹

Bolls plant⁻¹ showed a significant response to irrigation intervals, cultivars, and their interaction (Table 3). Irrigation with 25 days interval produced significantly more bolls per plant compared to all other irrigation intervals. Varietal mean revealed that CRIS-134 produced higher bolls count per plant compared with CRIS-342 and MNH-886. Interaction effect revealed that CRIS-134 in combination with 25 days irrigation interval, had the highest number of bolls per plant. Bolls per plant showed a curvilinear response to different irrigation intervals (Fig. 1c). Irrigation with 25 days interval had probably more favorable moisture content (19%) than lower or higher irrigation interval under ZT cotton which resulted in the development of more fruiting bodies (McVay *et al.*, 2006). Bolls per plant increased with an increase in irrigation intervals from 10 to 25; however, further increase beyond 25 days interval may not be productive for the reduced rate of boll growth. Higher bolls per plant might be due to better water availability, maximum water utilization at fruit-bearing stage, better maturity and ultimately better opening of bolls. A higher number of irrigation in cotton produced undesired excessive vegetative growth and more sympodial branches which may lead to dropping of bolls resulting in lower cotton yield (Wanjura *et al.*, 2002). These findings tallied with those of Ertek and Kanber (2001) who reported that an optimum number of irrigations could result in more boll formation. Further, they reported the number of bolls as a genetic parameter that differed for different cultivars (Ehsan *et al.*, 2008). Copur (2006) and Anwar *et al.* (2002) also had similar findings which reported that different varieties had a different number of bolls plant⁻¹ due to differences in their genetic potential.

Boll weight (g)

Boll weight showed a significant response to irrigation intervals, whereas interaction was not significant (Table 3). Results showed that irrigation with 25 days interval resulted in heavier bolls compared to 10, 15, and 20 days intervals. Regression analysis revealed that boll weight had a quadratic response to irrigation intervals (Fig. 1. d). Boll weight fluctuates between values of 2.3 and 2.9 with irrigation interval from 10 to 25 days. The regression equation indicates that 25 days irrigation interval is optimum for boll weight. This was probably because of increased translocation of photosynthates from source to sink (boll) due to more favorable soil environment for uptake of nutrients compared to all other irrigation regimes (as more moisture favored more vegetative growth rather than reproductive growth) (Dumka *et al.*, 2004). Heavier boll weight with 25 days

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irrigation interval was perhaps due to more favorable moisture condition for lesser evaporative losses from zero tillage cotton as reported by Silburn *et al.* (2007). Contrary to this shorter irrigation interval had lower boll weight probably due to more attacks of insect pests. Moreover, crop at shorter irrigation interval is more prone to insect pests, and diseases attack due to vigorous cotton plant growth. On the other hand, flowerings in too longer interval coincided with high moisture stress that also adversely affected boll growth and development (Yazar *et al.*, 2002; Naveed, 2003).

Seed cotton yield (kg ha⁻¹)

Results revealed that varieties, irrigation intervals, and varieties x irrigation interaction had significant effects on seed cotton yield (Table 3). Mean values for irrigation interval revealed that 25 days irrigation interval proved to be more productive regarding seed cotton yield than all other intervals. Irrigation intervals 10 to 20 days had lower seed cotton yield, perhaps due to excessive soil moisture that led to more dynamic vegetative growth rather than seed cotton yield. Besides higher seed cotton yield, irrigation with 25 days interval was cost-effective as it saved more water when compared with 10 days interval (check treatment for comparison). Varietal means revealed that CRIS-134 produced higher seed cotton yield while MNH-886 produced lower seed cotton yield. Interaction effect revealed that CRIS-134 in combination with 25 days irrigation interval produced higher seed cotton yields (Fig. 2. a). A trend line drawn for seed cotton yield in relation to irrigation intervals showed a quadratic response to an incremental increase in irrigation intervals (Fig. 2. b). It can be predicted from regression analysis that irrigation interval beyond 25 days may not be productive for the reduced rate of growth as a consequence of low moisture stress. Lower seed cotton yield with shorter irrigation intervals (10 to 20 days) might be due to excess moisture stress that led to flowers and bolls dropping (Ertek and Kanber, 2001). Similar findings were conveyed by Sahito *et al.* (2015) who reported that irrigation interval more than 20 days produced higher seed cotton yield. Optimum irrigation intervals probably improved root growth and consequent nutrient and water uptake resulted in higher seed cotton yield (Ertek and Kanber, 2001). Encisco *et al.* (2003), Guerra *et al.* (2002) and El-Shahawy and Abd-El-Malik (2005) had comparable findings which reported that moderate volume of irrigation would be more economical than excessive use of water. Furthermore, they reported that varieties with different genetic background had different seed cotton yields.

Ginning out turn (%)

GOT was significantly affected by irrigation intervals, cultivars, and their interaction (Table 4). It is evident from the results that 25 days irrigation interval produced highest GOT among all other irrigation intervals. Varietal means revealed that CRIS-134 produced higher GOT while MNH-886 produced lower GOT. Interaction effect revealed that CRIS-134 in combination with 25 days interval produced highest GOT (Fig. 2. c). Regression analysis revealed that there was an increase in GOT with the incremental increase in irrigation interval showing a quadratic trend line (Fig. 2. d). GOT had the almost similar response to irrigation intervals as mentioned for seed cotton yield. Every fortnight delay in irrigation beyond 25 days interval resulted in a significant decrease in GOT /lint yield (Karam *et al.*, 2006). Increased GOT might be associated with the physiological response to the culture under higher irrigation water (Cetin and Bilgel, 2002). In case of irrigation interval at 25 days the higher the water availability in the soil the greater the ability of the roots to absorb nutrients and the photosynthetic efficiency of the leaves. In case of irrigation interval at 25 days optimum water supply and higher nutrients absorption, contributed towards boll growth and boll filling that probably resulted in higher lint yield as confirmed by Rajput *et al.* (2006). Arshad *et al.* (2003) and Wang *et al.* (2004) recorded variable GOT among different varieties and reported that variation might be due to environmental or genetic factors/heterosis. The results of the present investigation are in line with previous findings by El-Shahawy and Abd-El-Malik (2005) and Abdel-Malak and Radwan (1998) who reported that GOT was associated with the genetic makeup of a variety.

Lint Index (g)

Lint index had a significant response to irrigation intervals, varieties and their interaction (Table 4). Results indicated that irrigation with 25 days interval produced higher lint index as compared to all other irrigation intervals. Among varieties, CRIS-134 had higher lint index amongst the other varieties. Interactive effects revealed that CRIS-134 with 25 days irrigation interval gave maximum lint index (Fig. 2. e). Higher lint index with 25 days irrigation interval was probably because of increased translocation of photosynthates from source to fiber (lint) due to more favorable soil environment for uptake of nutrients compared to all other irrigation regimes (Akhter et al. 2002). Contrary to this shorter irrigation interval had lower lint index probably due to more attacks of insect pests. Moreover, crop at shorter irrigation interval is more prone to insect pests, and diseases attack due to vigorous cotton plant growth. On the other hand, flowerings in too longer interval coincided with high moisture stress that also adversely affected lint index (Naveed, 2003; Ali et al., 2005).

Fiber length (mm)

Data pertaining to fiber length was affected significantly by irrigation intervals, cultivars, and their interaction (Table 4). Mean values revealed that irrigation with 25 days interval produced lengthier fibers compared to other irrigation intervals. Varietal means revealed that CRIS-134 produced higher fiber length while MNH-886 produced lower fiber length. Interaction effect revealed that CRIS-134 in combination with 25 days interval produced maximum fiber length of 28.8 mm (Fig. 3. a). Regression analysis showed that fiber length had a curvilinear response to irrigation intervals (Fig. 3. b). Fiber length is probably associated with the genetic makeup of a variety, but genotypes and environmental variation significantly affected fiber length (Tennakoon and Milroy, (2003); Tang et al., 2005). Ashokkumar and Ravikesavan (2011) reported that fiber length differed widely with genotypes and environment.

Fiber Strength (g tex^{-1})

Irrigation intervals affected fiber strength, whereas varieties and irrigation intervals \times varieties interaction were not significant (Table 4). Mean values revealed that irrigation intervals of 25 days had more fiber strength compared with 10, 15, and 20 days interval (Table 3). Fiber strength showed a quadratic trend line with respect to different irrigation intervals (Fig. 3. c). Trend line showed maximum value for fiber strength at 25 days irrigation interval. It can be predicted from regression analysis that increasing irrigation interval beyond 25 days may not result in significantly higher fiber strength for reduced growth rate. It is evident from the results that excess moisture stress affected vapor pressure deficits, and both canopy and leaf temperature resulted in reduced fiber strength (Bajwa and Vories, 2006). Gutstein (1997) also had analogous results, which reported that water in excess of cotton crop water requirement reduced fiber strength. Faircloth (2007) reported that fiber strength (g tex^{-1}) varied among cultivars.

Fiber micronaire ($\mu\text{g inch}^{-1}$)

Fiber micronaire values were significant for irrigation intervals, whereas non-significant for varieties and their interaction with irrigation intervals (Table 4). Irrigation interval of 25 days produced higher fiber micronaire compared with irrigation intervals. Other researchers also had identical results who communicated that different irrigation regimes significantly affected fiber micronaire (Balkcom *et al.*, 2006). Moreover, they reported that longer irrigation interval caused more fineness of the fiber. Although genotypes in the present study did not differ regarding micronaire value, however, Ehsan *et al.* (2008) and Copur (2006) remarked that varieties might be different in fiber fineness in different environments.

Conclusion

This study comprised of four irrigation intervals (10, 15, 20, and 25 days intervals) and three genotypes (MNH-886, CRIS-342, and CRIS-134). In conclusion, results of this study suggest that higher cotton yield and fiber characteristics can be attained, under Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan conditions, when cotton variety CRIS-134 is planted with 25 days irrigation interval.

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Table 1. Weather conditions at Cotton Research Station, Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan

The year 2017				
Month	Temperature °C			Rainfall (mm)
	Max.	Min.	Avg.	
May	38.9	23.4	31.1	15.0
June	41.8	27.0	28.5	6.0
July	45.0	27.2	31.5	126.0
Aug.	41.0	20.0	30.5	43.0
Sept.	40.0	18.0	29.0	40.0
Oct.	36.0	17.9	27.0	-
Nov.	27.8	10.4	19.1	3.0
Total rainfall (mm)				233.0

Table 2. Physico-chemical properties of the experimental soil

Characteristics	Values
Texture class	Silty Clay
Sand	151 g kg ⁻¹
Silt	450 g kg ⁻¹
Clay	400 g kg ⁻¹
Electrical conductivity (EC)	2.66 dSm ⁻¹
Soil pH (1:1)	7.80
Organic Matter	0.89 %
NO ₃ -N	5.52 mg kg ⁻¹
Available K (mg kg ⁻¹)	180 mg kg ⁻¹ soil
AB-DTPA extractable P	7.8 mg kg ⁻¹ soil
Total N	0.99 g kg ⁻¹ soil

Table 3. Irrigation intervals and cultivars effects on sympodia per plant, plant height, bolls/plant, boll weight, and seed cotton yield

Irrigation intervals (I)	Plant height (cm)	Sympodia/plant	bolls/plant	Boll weight (g)	Seed cotton yield (kg/ha)
10 days	131 a	14a	12 c	2.3 c	1647 d
15 days	124 b	11b	14 b	2.5 b	1891 c
20 days	114 c	8c	15 b	2.6 b	2095 b
25 days	105 d	7c	19 a	2.9 a	2424 a
LSD _{0.05}	5.71	1.76	1.27	0.13	67.38
Varieties (V)					
MNH-886	114	8 b	13 c	2.5	1740 c
CRIS-342	119	10 b	15 b	2.7	2027 b
CRIS-134	122	13 a	19 a	2.6	2275 a
LSD _{0.05}	-	1.73	0.64	-	47.94
Interaction p values	0.1368	0.4139	0.0002	0.2681	0.0058

Note: Means followed by a different letter (s) differ significantly at $P \leq 5\%$.

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Table 4. Irrigation intervals and varietal effects on ginning out turn, Fiber length, Fiber micronaire and Fiber strength of cotton

Irrigation intervals (I)	GOT (%)	Lint index (g)	Fiber length(mm)	Fiber strength (g /tex)	Micronaire ($\mu\text{g inch}^{-1}$)
10 days	31 d	2.96 d	25.5 d	27.6 d	3.1 c
15 days	33 c	3.48 c	25.9 c	28.4 c	3.2 bc
20 days	35 b	3.77 b	26.4 b	29.1 b	3.3 b
25 days	37 a	4.23 a	28.1 a	29.5 a	3.5 a
LSD _{0.05}	0.39	0.2344	0.16	0.31	0.12
Varieties (V)					
MNH-886	33 c	3.30 c	26.1 b	28.7	3.3
CRIS-342	34 b	3.58 b	26.2 b	28.7	3.2
CRIS-134	35 a	3.96 a	27.3 a	28.6	3.3
LSD _{0.05}	0.34	0.1447	0.14	-	-
Interaction P values	0.0000	0.0015	0.0105	0.3888	0.0593

Note: Means followed by a different letter (s) differ significantly at $P \leq 5\%$.

Fig. 1. Plant height (cm) (a), sympodia per plant (b), bolls per plant (c), and boll weight (g) as affected by

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irrigation intervals (days).

Fig. 2. (a) Interactive effect of genotypes x irrigation intervals on seed cotton yield, (b) Irrigation effect on seed cotton yield, (c) interactive effect of genotypes x irrigation intervals on GOT, (d) irrigation effect on GOT and

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(e) interactive effect of genotypes x irrigation intervals on lint index.

Fig. 3. (a) Effect of irrigation on fiber length, (b) interactive effect of genotypes x irrigation on fiber length, and

(c) irrigation effect on fiber strength.

Author's contribution

Niamat Ullah Khan conducted this research and prepared a draft of the paper. Fakhanda Khan supervised the study. Abdul Aziz Khakwani provided technical input at every step. Najeeb Ullah helped in lab analysis and literature collection. Abdul Qayum Khan helped in initial draft of the paper. Muhammad Kashan helped in lab work and analysis.

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